

VETERINARY SCIENCES

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY EVALUATIONS IN CRYPTOSPORIDIOSIS IN CALVES

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Abstract

This study took place from March to May 2019 and was conducted in the Farm 1 of Research and Development Institute for Cattle Balotești , Ilfov County. The aim was to establish guide values about incidence of cryptosporidiosis using speed tests (Rainbow Calf Scour 4) and parasitological exams : Ziehl – Nielsen staining, Anderson flotation method, zinc sulphate flotation associate with clinical signs.

From 10 calves, on coproparasitological exams using Ziehl – Nielsen staining from feces , was tested positive 2 calves by *Cryptosporidium* oocyst identification. On coproparasitological exams using zinc sulphate flotation was identificate *Eimeria unsporulate* oocyst and by speed tests (Rainbow Calf Scour 4) was detected one infection with coronavirus. Clinical signs was: diarrhea with yellow- green feces, tenesmus, cramps, loss of appetite, fever.

Keywords: cryptosporidiosis, calves, imunocromatography test Ziehl – Nielsen staining

Cryptosporidiosis, neonatal opportunistic sporozooisis, extends across the globe either under clinically , inapparent or sporadic forms or epidemic episodes in both human and animals. Following epidemiological investigations, cryptosporidiosis have been identified in sick animals and in the the clinically healthy ones from Scandinavia to Australia, the US and Europe to Japan, which shows the worldwide evolving character (Dărăbuș,,1996,2001). The various morphological , biological and genetic features differentiating species of *Cryptosporidium* from others is a major problem for practicing veterinarians and physicians in human medicine directly involved in the control of this morbid entity, in understanding the way in which the *Cryptosporidium* infection is transmitted . Also, a lot of studies reveal that, by means of routine clinical or microscopic examination, *Cryptosporidium* species involved in the infection cannot be exactly defined (Dărăbuș,,1997) . A study conducted in Romania upon 2802 cattle indicated that the most responsive age to Cryptosporidiosis is between 8-14 days. Significant differences were observed ($p < 0.001$) between infection at this age and other categories taken into account (Dărăbuș ,, 2001) . The incidence of infection decreases with age , so positive calves were not detected between the ages of six and twelve months. This decrease in infection extensity can be explained partly on account of age resistance and partly by the immunity gained from repeated contact with the parasite . The presence of a relatively high extensity (8.6%) of infection in cattle over the age of 3 years is probably due to the fact that this category was made up of newly calved cows exclusively (Akam, Dand colab.2001)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study took place from March 10 to May 4, 2019 and was conducted within Farm 1 at Research and Development Institute for Cattle in Balotești village , county of Ilfov , Romania on a total of 42 cattle aged 0-6 months . 10 calves were part of the study (6 males and 4 females), aged between 5 days to 4 weeks, 3 being raised in maternity and 7 in berth breeding system

Clinical examination

Serological by immunochromatography lateral flow - Quick Test Rainbow Calf Scour 4

Coproparasitological exams

Quick Test Rainbow Calf Scour 4

This test is composed of five devices each of them containing four strips (red -rotavirus, yellow-coronavirus , blue-e. Coli F5 (K99) and green- *Cryptosporidium parvum*) and five tubes with reagent and faeces sampling device. (Peeters, J., Villarcota, 2008)

PROCEDURE

1 - Take feces directly from the anus (if the feces are liquid will take a spatula full, (Fig.1).

2 – Homogenize feces and reagent in the tube and after homogenizing slightly flick the tube against a hard surface so that the liquid is collected at the bottom (Fig. 2)

3 – Remove the device from drying tube strips and the reagent tube is inserted therein (Fig.3).

4- Screw the cap with strips until you hear two clicks, which indicates piercing the septa of the reagent tube; then leave the device on a flat surface and wait for 10 minutes. The liquid in the tube will migrate to reactive strips (Fig. 4)

5 -After 10 minutes read results (Fig.5,6).

Fig.1 Sampling faeces

Fig.2 Reagent homogenization

Fig.3 Strip contact

Fig.4 Strip contact II

Fig.5 Reading results

Fig.6 Interpretation of results

Ziehl Neelsen method

Faeces smears are fixed with methanol or ethanol for 5 minutes. After removal of the alcohol and air drying, staining with Fuxin fennel (Fuxin Ziehl) for one hour. Stained preparations will be washed in tap water and then differentiated into a 2% solution of sulfuric acid for 20 seconds, stirring the slides continuously. After washing in tap water the slides will be stained for 5 minutes with 5% solution of malachite green. Rinse again in water, dried in air and examine x40 or x100 objective with immersion.

Cryptosporidiosis appear as spherical or ovoid formation of 4-6 microns, in vivid red color on a green bluish background. Their cytoplasm is granular, with a center often clearer and containing 0-6 sporozoites. By this technique, other non-acid-fast elements from faeces are stained by passing through sulfuric acid and then colored green due to counterstaining. Cells, bacteria and yeasts thus appear green, easily differentiating from Cryptosporidiosis. However, sometimes parasitic elements that do not stain or appear pink may occur, having the same shape and size with bright coloured oocysts. Other coccidia are also stained in vivid red colour, but they are larger. Moreover, there are also traces that appear to be round where oocysts have been placed (Kehl KS, 1995).

Flotation methods

Sheather's sucrose method

Faeces are homogenized with 2 ml formalin, filtered through cheesecloth and put it in a conical centrifuge. Sheather solution is added (500 g of sucrose were dissolved in 320 ml of distilled water containing 6.5 g phenol melted in water bath) until the centrifuge cup is full. Centrifugation is performed at 500 revolutions / min., for 15 minutes. It is a fast, sensitive method and it is recommended for screening.

Anderson's sucrose method

1-5 g faeces are mixed by 10-15 ml of water. Mix well and filtered through six layers of cheesecloth. The

filtrate is centrifuged 10 min at 500 rev / min. The deposit obtained is stirred with 10 ml of saturated sucrose solution after the formulations given below. Centrifuge again at 500 rev / min., for 10 minutes. The liquid from the surface of the centrifuged tube will be taken with a platinum loop, 4-7 micrometers in diameter and examined between microscope slides with x40 and x100 objectives immersion. Sucrose solution density is between 1.27 and 1.29. You can use two types of solutions of sucrose Sheather: -1500 G sucrose + 320 ml distilled water + 6.5 g of phenol;

Cryptosporidiosis oocysts appear as round microorganisms with a diameter of 5-6 micrometres fine-grained, with a prominent black spot (residual body). Intrinsic color ranging from pink to blue gray in light microscopy. Reading the slides should be made so as not to take more than one hour from execution as it destroys oocysts. Sucrose flotation, before staining methods, has the advantage that by concentrating parasitic elements makes it possible diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis, even in cases of poor infection. Cryptosporidiosis is recognized based on size, shape, colour and the presence of internal structures. Due to its complexity this method lends itself especially to confirm the diagnosis in doubtful evidence. It is not recommended for routine diagnosis. The effectiveness of the method has proven to be 100% in the diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis in fecal samples obtained from calves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Of the total of 10 calves in the study, a number of 2 heads (20%) were identified with Cryptosporidiosis, by coprological examination. The 10 samples collected were examined by two sucrose flotation techniques (Sheather and Anderson) and by staining Ziehl-Neelsen method. In a single sample *Cryptosporidium* oocysts were revealed by all the three methods, in the other one the method Sheather being negative. (Table 1)

Coproparasitological methods used in examination

Metode	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₄	P ₅	P ₆	P ₇	P ₈	P ₉	P ₁₀
Feces smear Ziehl-Neelsen stain	negativ	pozitiv	negativ	negativ	pozitiv	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ
Sheather flotation	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ	pozitiv	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ
Anderson flotation	negativ	pozitiv	negativ	negativ	pozitiv	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ	negativ

In Ziehl-Neelsen staining oocysts appear red, with various intensities, with the property of being acid-resistant which means they retain Fuxin Ziehl and after contact with the acid-alcohol solution they appear evident as compared to the blue or green background (Figure 7). Their size is 4-6 micrometres, egg-shaped, in

Fig.7 *Cryptosporidium*- oocyst (Ziehl-Neelsen staine)

which there constantly can be distinguished sporozoites, six in number arranged semicircular. In the samples examined their presence was not significant (Figure 8

Fig.8 *Cryptosporidium*- oocyst (Sheather method)

Serological quick test "Rainbow Calf Scour 4" positively identified one case, a calf aged 7 days, in maternity, that also presented positive reaction to Coronavirus infection. *Cryptosporidium* oocysts were detected by all three coproparasitological methods.

The usual flotation tests and McMaster method also identified *Eimeria* infections but only in individuals negative for *Cryptosporidium* tests

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